

More to Wave-equation Than Periodicity?

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The wave equation $\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } f(t)g(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } f(t) g(x)$ is well known for its periodic solution $\sin(\omega t) \sin(kx)$ (example). This solution means that: $\frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy}(\sin(\omega y)) = \text{constant} \sin(\omega y)$. An equally good solution is $\exp(ax)\exp(bt)$ except that this solution will have problems with boundary conditions. The point we make is that one does need to have a periodic function as a solution. The exp solution has the key feature that $\exp(ax_1)\exp(ax_2) = \exp(a(x_1+x_2))$, in other words this is linked with conservation for products of $\exp(ax)$. In other words, we argue that there are two key features associated with wave equations, periodicity and product probability/conservation scenarios and that one should be aware of both. In fact, we ultimately try to argue that the free particle quantum wavefunction contains both of these features and both are physical.

Returning to the periodic solution, the above implies that given $\sin(\omega y) + B \frac{d}{dy} \sin(\omega y)$, if one takes the derivative: $\frac{d}{dy}$, one obtains: $\frac{d}{dy} \sin(\omega y) + B \text{constant} \sin(\omega y)$. For certain values of B and constant, one may show that this linear combination satisfies: $\frac{d}{dx} f(x) = C_1 f(x)$. This has the formal solution of $f(x) = B \exp(C_1 x)$ which displays the additive feature (or conservation of probability, i.e. $\exp(C_1 x_1)\exp(C_1 x_2)$) of x . Thus, we suggest that one should focus on both the periodicity of $\sin(kx)$, $\sin(\omega t)$, but also on its link to conservation/probability. We suggest that both are key ideas and both manifest themselves in the free particle quantum wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In other words, there is more to a wave than its periodicity, we argue.

Wave-equation

The wave equation: $\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } f(t)g(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } f(t)g(x)$ ((1))

with a solution of $\sin(\omega t)\sin(kx)$ for example, seems to represent periodicity as its key feature. Certainly $\sin(\omega t)$ and $\sin(kx)$ are periodic (which is convenient for boundary conditions), but $\exp(ax)\exp(bt)$ is also a solution of the wave equation. In fact, one requires that:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} f(t) = \text{constant} f(t) \text{ and } \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} g(x) = \text{constant}^2 g(x) \text{ ((2))}$$

One solution is to have a function for which $\frac{d}{dt} f(t) = \text{constant} f(t)$, i.e. the $\exp(bt)$ solution. This solution is not periodic at all, but still satisfies the wave-equation. One may note that it will not match boundary conditions in most physical problems, but as far as the wave equation goes, it is a solution. Furthermore, its key feature is:

$$\exp(ax_1)\exp(ax_2) = \exp(a(x_1+x_2)) \text{ ((3)) or } \exp(a_1x)\exp(a_2x) = \exp(x(a_1+a_2))$$

If there is a reason to multiply two solutions (as in the AND case of probability), then one sees that a_1+a_2 represents a conserved quantity with probability the same for all $\exp(a_1x)\exp(a_2x)$ such that $a_i+a_j=a_1+a_2$.

Considering the wave-equation without boundary conditions suggests that a periodic solution is no more relevant than one linked with probability which conserves a quantity. The question is: Can one have both?

Periodicity and Probability with Conservation

The condition ((2)) suggests the following. If one writes:

$$m(x) = g(x) + B \frac{d}{dx} g(x) \rightarrow \frac{dm}{dx} = \frac{dg}{dx} + B C g(x) \quad ((4))$$

We assume that $g(x)$ is periodic and real. Consider $g(x)$ at $x=0$ (by shifting the origin). $g(x)$ rises, hits a maximum, falls back to 0 etc if the y axis is placed in a certain position. In the rising part of $g(x)$, $\frac{d}{dx} g(x)$ also is a positive number, but $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} g(x)$ is negative.

We wish to have: $\frac{dm}{dx} = C m$. Now C in ((4)) must be negative for the above reason, but $\frac{dg}{dx}$ is positive. Thus, there is a relative sign problem in ((4)) unless one counteracts it by letting $B=i$ and $C = \text{constant } i$. Thus, the periodic function $g(x)$ can be used to create a solution of

$$\frac{dm}{dx} = \text{constant } m \quad \text{if} \quad m = g(x) + i \frac{d}{dx} g(x) \quad ((5))$$

As an example, consider $g(x) = \cos(x)$.

The point we make, however, is that $\frac{dm}{dx} = C m \rightarrow m = B_1 \exp(Cx) \quad ((6))$

The solution ((6)) satisfies the conditions of a probability which is linked with conservation, i.e.

$$\exp(c_1 x) \exp(c_2 x) = \exp((c_1 + c_2)x) \quad ((7))$$

We see that the periodic solution $g(x)$ may be used in a function ((5)) containing the imaginary i to create a new function which behaves as a complex probability which conserves a quantity. One may have this probability/conservation feature and periodicity together. We suggest that both of these features are key physically.

In fact, we suggest that the function:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad \hbar = 1 \quad ((8))$$

, the free particle wavefunction, relies on both. The periodic feature is very well-known as:

$$\text{Period} = \hbar/E \quad \text{and} \quad \text{wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((9))$$

, but the product probability/conservation feature does not seem to be stressed as much (we argue).

This probability/conservation feature is key in ensuring conservation of momentum and energy, i.e.

$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(ip_3x)\exp(ip_4x)$ if $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$ (one dimension) ((10)) etc

Thus, both periodicity and product probability/conservation are part of the wave picture, we argue.

Conclusion

The wave-equation $1/c^2 \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } f(t)g(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } f(t)g(x)$ is usually associated with the solution $\sin(\omega t)\sin(kx)$ (or a variant), i.e. a periodic solution which is convenient for matching boundary conditions. $\exp(at)\exp(bx)$, however, is equally as good a solution of the differential equation (ignoring the boundary conditions). This solution has no periodicity, but has the feature: $\exp(bx_1)\exp(bx_2) = \exp(b(x_1+x_2))$ or (one may use x as the variable and choose b_1 and b_2). In other words, there seems to be a conserved quantity.

Here, we try to show that one may have both periodicity and this product/conservation feature. In fact, a solution to the wave equation requires that $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} g(x) = C g(x)$. Thus, $g(x) + B \frac{dg}{dx} = m(x)$ can be made into a solution of $\frac{dm}{dx} = c^2 m(x)$, as we show above, if one uses purely imaginary numbers. One may have periodicity in a solution as well as the product/conservation law feature. This, we argue, is key for free particle quantum mechanics as the wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ has both. The periodicity is linked with the physical period and wavelength, while the product probability/conservation law is linked with conservation of momentum and energy. Thus, one should be aware of both features, we argue and not simply the periodicity linked with a wave-equation.